

THE ROLE OF WORKS OF ART IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND WORK ON THEM

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages.

Department of Theory of English Language and Literature

Sh. O. Mamayakubova

E-mail: mamayakubovashahlo@gmail.com

Rasulova Gulasal Azizjan qizi

Students of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. This articles is devoted to the role of works of art in learning a foreign language and the process of working on them, which is considered the most important issue in the field of aducation today. The article reflects on the importance of using the types of articles works and analysis methods in the effective organization of learning lessons.

Key words: a work of art, world literature, fairy tale, story, speech, to memorize, riddle, proverb.

In elementary grades, stories, fairy tales, parables, proverb and riddles are practically studied among the types of works of art. Also popular scientific articles are taught. Works vary in genre and each has its own characteristics and impact on readers. Accordingly, the teacher is required to choose appropriate procedures and methods for teaching each work. A story is a short work that summarizes a certain event, that is, the important aspects of life. There are many works written in the genre of stories in foreign literature. In elementary grades, it is necessary to read stories written in English, to open up its content, to work on academic words or phrases presented in the story, and to apply the method of retelling the text. The content of the story is analyzed on the basis of questions or exercises given on the subject. It is also important to explain the meaning of

words and phrases that pupils do not comprehend in the story, otherwise they will not be able to understand the content of the story and it will be difficult to complete the given tasks. Should be able to know what the story is about, what the maintenance is, remember and interpret significant sentences or keywords, without having to spend time translating an entire story. Having an realizing of the story and thinking about it, they will be able to complete the tasks. Topic cards or exercises related to the story help to improve pupil's skills. This method is effective for increasing pupils' vocabulary while learning a foreign language.

In addition, it is very significant for elementary schools to learn poems, riddles and proverbs in a foreign language. In which pupils' pronunciation improves and their level increases. In the process of studying a foreign language, if the correct pronunciation is learned from the first days of the lessons, then there will be no difficulty in the process of memorizing academic words of a higher level.

In conclusion, it is necessary to use new child-friendly methods of foreign language teaching in preschool and elementary education, that is, to memorize a lot of poems and riddles, to sing songs written in ordinary children's language through games. As well as teaching short story and fairy tales are very effective. In increase their interest in the language. Young children have a strong memory and most of the learned knowledge is retained. With this in mind , establishing languages at a young age is beneficial.

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